

LIFE SKILLS AMONG SCHEDULED TRIBE UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS OF BILASPUR

Kazi Masud Hossain, Chandrakali & Dr. Budh Singh

¹*Research Scholar, Department of Education, Guru Ghasidas Vishwavidyalaya, Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh*

²*Research Scholar, Department of Education, Guru Ghasidas Vishwavidyalaya, Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh*

³*Associate Professor, Department of Education, Guru Ghasidas Vishwavidyalaya, Bilaspur, Chhattisgarh*

Paper Received On: 20 May 2024

Peer Reviewed On: 24 June 2024

Published On: 01 July 2024

Abstract

This study investigates the life skills of scheduled tribe undergraduate students in Bilaspur, focusing on gender, stream of study, locality, type of institution, and nature of institution. Using a descriptive survey research design, data were collected from 50 scheduled tribe undergraduate students residing in a government hostel through random sampling. The Life Skills Scale (LSS-KCTA) by Chandra Kumari and Ayushi Tripathi, comprising 52 items with high reliability (0.90), was employed. Finding of the study reveal a significant difference in life skill scores between male and female students, with males scoring higher. However, no significant differences were found across other demographic and institutional factors, indicating uniformity in life skill levels among scheduled tribe undergraduate students regardless of institutional and demographic characteristics. These findings highlight the importance of addressing gender disparities in life skill development while recognizing the overall consistency in life skill levels within this population.

Keywords: *Life Skill, Scheduled Tribe, Undergraduate students*

Introduction

Education unfolds the hidden potentials of an individual and transforms him/her into a wholesome being. It prepares the students for life, to enable them to face the challenges of life. According to Dellor's Commission report (1996), the world is developing very fast, and progress also coming very close, with increasing interdependence in individuals at local,

National, and International levels and this also leads to new problems and challenges in individuals daily life. Future human progress relies less on steady economic expansion and more on expanding individual growth and being empowered, which are crucial to directing overall progress wisely. So, education should not be confined to acquiring information for knowledge, passing exams, and getting a job only but today's changes and challenges of a fast-growing society and world demand more skills to cope with real-life situations. A child with life skills can effectively handle resources and overcome challenges in life, especially in dealing with many kinds of hardship (Srikala and Kishor, 2010). The prime focus, therefore, needs an extraordinary emphasis on developing life skills in Students so that they can cope with existing and future challenges, and live a quality life (Prajapati, Sharma, and Sharma, 2017). According to the World Health Organization (1997), life skills involve "capabilities" for positive and adaptive behavior which assist individuals in managing the demands and difficulties of daily life." 'Adaptive' implies flexibility and the ability to cope with the times, while 'positive behavior' refers to maintaining optimism and looking ahead even through adversity. Life skill education includes an asset of interrelated skills that should empower children and adolescents to lead a healthy, successful life and assume social responsibility (Who,1994; WHO,2003; Buehler,2016; UNICEF,2019).

Adolescents are in a stage of lifespan development where they face challenges with distinct needs and demands. It is a critical stage for everyone's life which consists of a period of transition from childhood to adulthood. This period represents, in many cases, a phase when a foundation is laid for a booming career and a fruitful life. To help adolescents in this dilemmatic phase of challenge and opportunity education system should come forward and provide a helping hand to adolescents. The educational system needs to give students the best possible chance to concentrate on acquiring knowledge, abilities, views, and values. Unfortunately, today's education focuses on the acquisition of knowledge and the attainment of degrees. One of the measures to improve this situation is the integration of life skills into the school curriculum. The National Curriculum Framework (NCF) 2005 outlines several key objectives for education. It emphasizes that students should develop independent thinking skills, both individually and in groups. Additionally, fostering emotional intelligence is crucial for students to thrive in a challenging world with satisfaction and success. Understanding others, cooperation, social responsibility, and strong interpersonal relationships are equally important for both teachers and students. These objectives can be effectively achieved by integrating life skills into the teaching and learning process. The

Copyright © 2024, Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies

National Education Policy (NEP), 2020 of the Ministry of Education, India, highlights the significance of moving away from traditional rote learning methods and enabling young learners to develop life skills that will assist them make sound choices regarding what they do both inside and outside of the classroom.

Research Gap:

The development of life skills in students helps them to face the challenges of life and cope with problematic situations. Life Skills means the ability to become active and take the responsibility of behaving in a particular manner, in a particular situation for healthy living. Various studies have highlighted the importance of Life Skills and Life Skills Education. Life Skills are important as they help adolescents to transit successfully from childhood to adulthood, develop psycho-social competence, prevent the abuse of tobacco, and promote positive self-esteem (Kumar & Chhabra, 2014). Life Skills education must be promoted among adolescents with the help of schools as Life Skills are needed for the Introduction of socialization of students (Awasthi & Kumari, 2011). Life skills education must be included in the school curriculum as life skills make the lives of adolescents valuable and convert them to individuals of high potential. Life skills education enables young people to take positive action to protect themselves. It also promotes health and positive social relationships with others in society (Aparna & Rakhee, 2011). Various research has been done to find the efficacy of Life Skills education programs. Parvathy & Pillai (2015) did a study to find the impact of life skills education on adolescents in rural schools. Their study revealed a significant impact of Life Skills Education on adolescents. Pujar, Hunshal & Bailur (2014) did a study to find the impact of intervention on life skills development among adolescent girls. They found the intervention program on life skills was helpful for rural adolescent girls to take positive actions. Yadav & Iqbal (2009) found positive results of life skills training in bringing change in adolescents' attitudes, thoughts, and behavior. Malik, Anand, Karamvir, &Batra (2012) found that there was a significant decrease in academic anxiety post-intervention of life skills training provided to students. David & John (2011) found a positive correlation between Life skills and attitude towards vocation. The National Education Policy 2020 also recognizes the importance of soft skills such as communication, teamwork, problem-solving, decision-making, and analytical thinking as imperative life skills. In today's society, students' life has become very fast and stressful. A student has to perform different activities within a limited time. Sometimes it becomes very difficult to perform all the activities effectively. The challenges that most students face today are failure in

Copyright © 2024, Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies

examinations, attainment of marks lower than expected, cutthroat competition, etc. A prolonged period of stress could lead to severe life frustration. Time constraints and stress can make it difficult for pupils to enjoy life while maintaining relationships with others. Support is therefore vital in reducing this unpleasant condition. Every learner has different obstacles to overcome and needs distinct skills to do so. In these kinds of circumstances, life skills can be quite helpful in assisting pupils in overcoming their challenges. Basic education must include instruction in life skills to advance gender equality, democracy, good citizenship, child care, protection equality, and educational system efficiency. The significance of developing and implementing life skills programs in Indian schools, colleges, and institutions cannot be overstated.

Chhattisgarh is home to a population of diverse ethnic, social, religious, and linguistic backgrounds. More than one-third of the State's residents officially belong to Scheduled Castes or Scheduled Tribes. About 31 percent belong to more than 43 tribes, including particularly vulnerable tribal groups. Older adolescents (14-18 years of age) in rural areas are not learning in schools and are not equipped with the skills and abilities they will need to be ready for productive lives as adults (ASER, 2017). There is an urgent need for research to develop the life skills of tribal children. Hence, no study has been conducted on life skills among tribal students of Chhattisgarh; therefore, it is important to identify the level and relevance of life skills to tribal students. This would give the insight to explore life skills among tribal students at the secondary level and develop a suitable life skill development program.

Objectives of the study

1. To study the life skills among scheduled tribe undergraduate students of Bilaspur.
2. To study the difference between the life skills of scheduled tribe undergraduate students of Bilaspur with reference to:
 - Gender (Female & Male)
 - Stream (Arts & Science)
 - Locality (Rural & Urban)
 - Types of Institution (College & University)
 - Nature of Institution (Govt. & Private)

Hypothesis

The following null hypotheses were formulated for the present study

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in life skills of scheduled tribe undergraduate students of Bilaspur with reference to their gender

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in life skills of scheduled tribe undergraduate students of Bilaspur with reference to their stream

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in life skills of scheduled tribe undergraduate students of bilaspur with reference to their locality

H₀₄: There is no significant difference in life skills of scheduled tribe undergraduate students of bilaspur with reference to their types of institution

H₀₅: There is no significant difference in life skills of scheduled tribe undergraduate students of Bilaspur with reference to their nature of institution

Method

The study adopted a descriptive survey research design to collect data from scheduled tribe undergraduate students residing in a government hostel in Bilaspur. The population of interest included all scheduled tribe students enrolled in undergraduate programs and staying in the specified hostel. Using random sampling, 50 participants were selected from the hostel, ensuring equal representation of both genders.

Tool Used:

In order to carry out the present study, the appropriate tool was used, which is mentioned below.

Life Skills Scale (LSS-KCTA) by Chandra Kumari and Ayushi Tripathi

This tool consists of 52 items (life skills scale) comprising 26 positively worded statement and 26 negatively worded statements. The scale has been standardized and exhibits high reliability, with a reliability coefficient of 0.90. The reliability of the scale has been established using the Spearman-brown correlation coefficient. To ensure validity, content validity and face validity has been employed.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

The data were processed using the statistical software package SPSS 26.0. Descriptive statistics including mean, frequency, and standard deviation were computed to summarize the data. Additionally, an independent samples t-test was employed to investigate potential differences in life skill based on variables such as gender, location, stream, nature of institute and type of institute.

Objective-1. To study the life skills among scheduled tribe undergraduate students of Bilaspur.

Table 1.

Level of life skills among scheduled tribe undergraduate students of Bilaspur.

Level of Life Skills	High	Average	Low
Male (N=25) (0)	72% (18)	28% (7)	0%
Female (N=25) (0)	44% (11)	56% (14)	0%
Total (N=50) (0)	58% (29)	42% (21)	0%

It is inferred from the above table that the majority of scheduled tribe undergraduate students in Bilaspur possess high life skills, with 58% (29 out of 50) of the students falling into the 'High' category. A considerable 42% percentage (21 out of 50) of the students displays average life skills. These students have a moderate level of competency in the key areas of life skills. And none of the students fall into the low life skills category. This is a positive outcome, indicating that all the surveyed students have at least a basic level of life skills.

Based on the above table, we can interpret that a significant majority of male scheduled tribe undergraduate students in Bilaspur, 72%, possess high life skills, indicating that 18 out of the 25 male students have a strong proficiency in this area. Meanwhile, 28% of the male students, equating to 7 out of 25, have average life skills. Notably, none of the male students are categorized as having low life skills, which is a positive indicator that all the male students in this study possess at least an average level of life skills.

According to the above table, it can be also interpreted that a marginal number of female scheduled tribe undergraduate students in Bilaspur, 44%, possess high life skills, indicating that 11 out of the 25 female students have a strong proficiency in this area. Meanwhile, 56% of the female students, equating to 14 out of 25, have average life skills. Notably, none of the female students are categorized as having low life skills, which is a positive indicator that all the female students in this study possess at least an average level of life skills.

Objective 2: Under Objective 2, the results are discussed based on five categorical variables:
Objective 2.1: To study the life skill of scheduled tribe undergraduate students of Bilaspur with reference to their gender.

The Objective was to compare mean score of life skill of male and female scheduled tribe undergraduate students. The data were analyzed with the help of t-test and the results are given in Table 2.

Table 2
Group Statistics and Independent Samples t test_Life skill of undergraduate students _ Gender

<i>Group Statistics</i>		<i>t-test for Equality of Means</i>				
	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
Life skill	Female	25	173.04	13.243	2.370	.022
	Male	25	183.36	17.282		

Table 2 shows that among scheduled tribe undergraduate female students, the mean life skill score is 173.04 with a standard deviation of 13.243, while for scheduled tribe undergraduate male students, the mean score is 183.36 with a standard deviation of 17.282. In case of comparing the mean score of life skill of female and male scheduled tribe undergraduate students, the calculated t value is 2.370 and the calculated p-value is .022 ($p < 0.05$). Since p value is less than 0.05, hence p value is significant at .05 level. So H_0 is not accepted and it can be safely said that there is significant difference between female and male scheduled tribe undergraduate students in respect to their life skill.

Objective No 2.2: To study the life skill of scheduled tribe undergraduate students of Bilaspur with reference to their type of institution.

The Objective was to compare mean score of life skill of college and university scheduled tribe undergraduate students. The data were analyzed with the help of t-test and the results are given in Table 3.

Table 3
Group Statistics and Independent Samples t test_Life skill of undergraduate students _
Type of Institution

<i>Group Statistics</i>		<i>t-test for Equality of Means</i>				
	Type of Institution	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
Life skill	College	36	178.24	16.483	0.058	.954
	University	14	177.75	12.659		

Table 3 shows that among college students, the mean life skill score is 178.24 with a standard deviation of 16.483, while for university students, the mean score is 177.75 with a standard deviation of 12.659. In case of comparing the mean score of life skill between college and university scheduled tribe undergraduate students, the calculated t value is 0.058 and the calculated p-value is .954 ($p > 0.05$). Since p value is more than 0.05, hence p value is not significant at .05 level. So H_0 is accepted and it can be safely said that there is no significant difference between college and university scheduled tribe undergraduate students in respect to their life skill.

Objective No 2.3: To study the life skill of scheduled tribe undergraduate students of Bilaspur with reference to their locale.

The Objective was to compare mean score of life skill of rural and urban scheduled tribe undergraduate students. The data were analyzed with the help of t-test and the results are given in Table 4.

Table 4
Group Statistics and Independent Samples t test_Life skill of undergraduate students _
Locale

<i>Group Statistics</i>		<i>t-test for Equality of Means</i>				
	Locale	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
Life skill	Rural	35	177.66	14.357	0.361	.720
	Urban	15	179.47	20.117		

Table 4 shows that among scheduled tribe undergraduate rural students, the mean life skill score is 177.66 with a standard deviation of 14.357, while for scheduled tribe

undergraduate urban students the mean score is 179.47 with a standard deviation of 20.117. In case of comparing the mean score of life skill between rural and urban scheduled tribe undergraduate students, the calculated t value is 0.361 and the calculated p-value is .720 ($p > 0.05$). Since p value is more than 0.05, hence p value is not significant at .05 level. So H_03 is accepted and it can be safely said that there is no significant difference between rural and urban scheduled tribe undergraduate students in respect to their life skill.

Objective No 2.4: To study the life skill of scheduled tribe undergraduate students of Bilaspur with reference to their stream.

The Objective was to compare mean score of life skill of humanities and science scheduled tribe undergraduate students. The data were analyzed with the help of t-test and the results are given in Table 5.

Table 5
Group Statistics and Independent Samples t test_Life skill of undergraduate students _ Stream

<i>Group Statistics</i>		<i>t-test for Equality of Means</i>				
	Stream	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	Sig. (2-tailed)
Life skill	Humanities	12	174.42	15.785	0.932	.356
	Science	38	179.39	16.226		

Table 5 shows that that among humanities scheduled tribe undergraduate students, the mean life skill score is 174.66 with a standard deviation of 15.785, while for science scheduled tribe undergraduate students the mean score is 179.47 with a standard deviation of 20.117. In case of comparing the mean score of life skill between humanities and science scheduled tribe undergraduate students, the calculated t value is 0.932 and the calculated p-value is .356 ($p > 0.05$). Since p value is more than 0.05, hence p value is not significant at .05 level. So H_04 is accepted and it can be safely said that there is no significant difference between humanities and science scheduled tribe undergraduate students in respect to their life skill.

Objective No 2.4: To study the life skill of scheduled tribe undergraduate students of Bilaspur with reference to their nature of institution.

The Objective was to compare mean score of life skill of govt. and private scheduled tribe undergraduate students. The data were analyzed with the help of t-test and the results are given in Table 6.

Table 6
Group Statistics and Independent Samples t test_Life skill of undergraduate students _
Nature of Institution

		<i>Group Statistics</i>		<i>t-test for Equality of Means</i>		
	Nature of Institution	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	Sig.(2-tailed)
Life skill	Govt.	37	177.78	15.773	.305	.836
	Private	13	179.38	17.624		

Table 6 shows that that among govt. scheduled tribe undergraduate students, the mean life skill score is 177.78 with a standard deviation of 15.773, while for private scheduled tribe undergraduate students the mean score is 179.38 with a standard deviation of 17.624. In case of comparing the mean score of life skill between govt. and private scheduled tribe undergraduate students, the calculated t value is 0.305 and the calculated p-value is .836 ($p > 0.05$). Since p value is more than 0.05, hence p value is not significant at .05 level. So H_0 is accepted and it can be safely said that there is no significant difference between govt. and private scheduled tribe undergraduate students in respect to their life skill.

Findings

The findings of the study are given below.

1. The majority of scheduled tribe undergraduate students in Bilaspur possess high life skills.
2. A higher proportion of male students (72%) have high life skills compared to female students (44%). This indicates that male students are more likely to possess high life skills.
3. Conversely, a higher proportion of female students (56%) fall into the 'Average' category compared to male students (28%). This suggests that while female students have sufficient life skills, fewer of them reach the highest level of proficiency compared to their male counterparts.

4. Neither male nor female students fall into the 'Low' category, which is a positive indication that all students have at least an average level of life skills.
5. There is a significant difference in life skill scores between male and female scheduled tribe undergraduate students, with males scoring higher than females.
6. There is no significant difference in life skill scores between college and university scheduled tribe undergraduate students.
7. There is no significant difference in life skill scores between rural and urban scheduled tribe undergraduate students.
8. There is no significant difference in life skill scores between humanities and science scheduled tribe undergraduate students.
9. There is no significant difference in life skill scores between government and private scheduled tribe undergraduate students.

Discussion:

The study findings reveal several insights regarding the life skill scores of scheduled tribe undergraduate students. Notably, there exists a significant disparity between genders, with male students demonstrating higher scores compared to their female counterparts. However, no significant distinctions were observed based on the type of institution attended (college or university), the rural or urban background of students, the field of study (humanities or science), or the nature of institution (government or private). These results underscore the importance of addressing gender-based differences in life skill development among scheduled tribe undergraduate students, while also highlighting the overall consistency in life skill levels across various demographic and institutional factors within this population.

Conclusion:

In conclusion, the findings of this study shed light on the nuanced landscape of life skill development among scheduled tribe undergraduate students. The significant discrepancy observed between male and female students underscores the need for targeted interventions to address gender-specific challenges and foster equitable skill development opportunities. However, the overall consistency in life skill levels across factors such as institution type, rural/urban background, field of study, and institutional affiliation suggests a relatively uniform distribution of life skill competencies within this demographic. Moving forward, it is imperative for educational institutions and policymakers to implement tailored strategies aimed at promoting holistic skill development while also addressing gender-based disparities

Copyright © 2024, Scholarly Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies

to ensure the equitable growth and success of all scheduled tribe undergraduate students. Additionally, further research is warranted to delve deeper into the underlying factors contributing to these disparities and to inform the design of more effective interventions tailored to the specific needs of this diverse student population.

References

- Aparna, N., & Raakhee, A. S. (2011). *Life Skill Education for Adolescents: Its Relevance and Importance*. *GESJ: Education Science and Psychology*, 2(9), 3–7.
- Awasthi, & Kumari. (2011). *Developing Life Skill for reproduction Health among Adolescent Girls*. *Journal of on International Academicians Global Education and Society*, 2(4). *Comprehensive-lifeskills-framework.pdf*. (n.d.). Retrieved June 28, 2024, from <https://www.unicef.org/india/media/2571/file/Comprehensive-lifeskills-framework.pdf>
- David, B., & John, S. (2011). *Life Skills and Attitude towards Vocation among the Vocational Higher Secondary and Higher Secondary School Students*. *EduTracks*, 10(8), 16–18. *Escap_peers_07.pdf*. (n.d.). Retrieved June 28, 2024, from https://www.unodc.org/pdf/youthnet/action/message/escap_peers_07.pdf
- Global Evaluation of Life Skills Education Programmes*. (2012). UNICEF.
- Kumar, J., & Chhabra, A. (2014). *Life skill education for adolescents: Coping with challenges*. *Scholarly Research Journal for Humanity Science and English Language*, 1(2), 181–190.
- Malik, A., Anand, M., Karamvir, & Batra, A. (2012). *Effect of life skill training on academic anxiety, adjustment and self-esteem levels in early adolescents*. *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*, 38(1), 188–192.
- Parvathy, V., & Pillai, R. R. (2015). *Impact of Life Skills Education on Adolescents in Rural School*. *International Journal of Advanced Research*, 3(2), 788–794.
- Prajapati, R., Sharma, B., & Sharma, D. (2016). *Significance Of Life Skills Education*. *Contemporary Issues in Education Research (CIER)*, 10(1), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.19030/cier.v10i1.9875>
- Pujar, L., Hunshal, S., & Bailur, K. (2014). *Impact of intervention on life skill development among adolescent girls*. *Karnataka Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 2(7), 93–94.
- Skills for Health*. (2003). World Health Organization.
- Srikala, B., & Kumar, K. (2010). *Empowering adolescents with life skills education in schools – School mental health program: Does it work?* *Indian Journal of Psychiatry*, 52(4), 344–349. <https://doi.org/10.4103/0019-5545.74310>
- The jamovi project* (2023). *jamovi*. (Version 2.4) [Computer Software]. Retrieved from <https://www.jamovi.org>.
- The World Health Organization Life Skills Education for Children and Adolescents in Schools”- Programme on Mental Health*. (1997). World Health Organization, Geneva. <https://www.scribd.com/document/32430059/Life-Skills-Have-Been-Defined-by-the-World-Health-Organization>
- Yadav, P., & Iqbal, N. (2009). *Impact of Life Skill Training on Self-Esteem, Adjustment and Empathy among Adolescents*. *Journal of the Indian Academy of Applied Psychology*, 35, 61–70.